
The songs of Sufferings: Position Grand Predicaments Ben Okri in Songs of Enchantment, Infinite Riches, and the Famished Road

P.Sankar, Department of English, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Arts & Science, Dharmapuri, Tamilnadu

**Paper Received on 06-12-2022, Accepted on 06-01-2023,
Published on 08-01-23;DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.1.42**

Abstract

Magical realism is used as a literary mode to highlight the significance of cultural intermingling, hybridity, and transformation. In the Novel 'Songs of Enchantment', Nigerian author Ben Okri uses dreams, visions, and magic to connect politics and history to bring out the concept of African consciousness in postcolonial society. The paper focuses on using imagination and its purpose in the novel. The mode of magical realism in the book helps the reader to view postcolonial Nigeria through dreams which serve in two ways firstly, through culture and society, and secondly, through hope of postcolonial Nigeria. This study aims to analyze how Okri encodes African consciousness versus Western epistemology and reevaluates history through dreams and visions. Further, the study tries to analyze how Okri redreams postcolonial Nigeria through the third eye in 'Songs of Enchantment.'

Keywords: Dreams, Visions, postcolonial Nigeria, culture and society, Songs of Enchantment.

Introduction

Ben Okri, the position Grand and post-modern novelist of Nigeria, has won many accolades to his credit. The paper intends to investigate his second novel, titled 'The songs of Enchantment', the sequel to his trilogy of magic realism. The story is a continual journey of the spirit of Azaro through the traverses of political campaigning between the Party of the Rich on one side and the Party of the Poor on the other. The novelist plagues the political incorrectness and the commotions that haunt the village of Azaro. He has outwitted death in the first novel, 'The Famished Road', and continues his journey across political trajectories in the radiant sequel of the book.

The second segment of the 'Famished Road' has a relatively shorter version of his physicality but gains a lofty motif by blending the political with the supernatural. The ease of the novel lies in its simplicity of language and structure. The complexity lies in integrating the philosophical and aesthetic dimensions to bring about a political platform, as seen through the eyes of the spirit of Azaro. Therefore, the novel cautions the reader that the narration is not a continuous fairytale but offers a severe note of the beginnings of a new possibility in terms

of its meaning and being. Gabriel Okara, in his work, Post Colonial African Writers :

Bibliographical Critical Sourcebook opines the differences between the sequel and the prequel as Songs of Enchantment brilliantly demonstrates Okri's ability to combine the traditions of realism, modernism, and African oral traditions. The novelist describes the adventures of Azaro, who has difficulty deciding which world he wants to embrace.....A reduction in lyrical grandeur and philosophical complexity pays for songs of Enchantment. Okri's characters undergo many subtle changes and re-evaluations in the second novel. (369)

Grand Predicaments in Songs of Enchantment And Infinite Riches

Madame Koto is presented as an incarnation of evil by her constant oppression and exploitation of the poor. The people of the society and the companions of Azaro, like, The Silent Woman, The one-eyed spirits, White Horse, etc., are on the bandwagon of the political ring.

They fear witches and wizards and take the side of the most powerful who would protect them from all oddities. Koto begins to disrupt peace in the novel by making dubious incantations and offering sacrifices. She also buries white beads in the night and unearths them in the daylight as a ritual to testify her victory. Politicians entrap the people with their sinister gifts. They feed these people with Milk which turns rotten and

sour. There are also instances where people are beaten up by the politicians and their supporters who put up stalls encroaching on the space of the rival parties. Madam koto questions her people thus. What does it take to make you people fear me? My enemies will turn to

Stone will go mad, blind, lose their legs and hands, and forget who they are. Their wives will give birth to children who will torment them. And some will give birth to goats, rats, and snakes. The rock is my power (193).

The novel also projects the misdeeds and third-rate means the politicians use to win the elections. On the one hand, there are offerings and gifts. On the other hand, they use money and physical force to win the elections. The primary question that the author wants one to understand is the existence of ghosts and spirits. One of the basic tenets of magic realism is the ability to look at reality from a different perspective, a dimension that can foresee the truth from a flip side. The story has elements of ghosts, spirits, and dreams that prove that the locale of Africa is much infested by the belief in the supernatural that makes the ordinary sound extraordinary. Okri, in his description, discusses more visual sensualities in the contexts of ghosts and spirits. For example, in one of the descriptions, he talks about a red heart that pulls onto a white horse and gets on top of it. One cannot question the color

consciousness but rather look at the perspective of looking beyond what is plausible and feasible in a storyline. There are also descriptions of humans who are more scary and horrific. In the novel, one can find the definition of Women with almond eyes, long fingernails, and lace dresses floated past boiling cigarettes in their hands. They were short men with powerful heads and small eyes, tall men with servants who fanned them, and stocky men with tired eyes. The red lights made everything unreal, and I kept going up to people and touching their stomachs. (99)

The novelist employs a judicious mixture of animals and spirits because, partly, they are mythical. They mainly symbolize the repressed dreams of the author, who wanted much freedom not only politically but also psychologically in postcolonial Africa. It is psychologically inferred that a colonized country wants to come out of its colonial trauma after the colonizers have granted it liberty. These hangovers of the colonial past wreak them an irrevocable vengeance on the colonizers by trying to establish their lost identity in the past and reclaim their land long lost to the white people. Therefore it is common for any writer from a third-world country to not use dream imageries to reinstate his lost identity. The classic examples could be the dad's struggles with his constant vision impediments and altercations with the political mercenaries. Azaro also talks

about the imaginary fight of the dad with the dragons and his winning over the warriors. The compulsory route in the novel is that ghosts throughout the story replace humans. This is to constantly signify the lost connections Azaro had with his ancestors and make a world more ethnic in terms of the African spirits, both physical and psychological, through the trajectories of the novel. The ghosts that Azaro sees are the ones that are selfish and crave space and an opportunity where their dreams can be fulfilled so that they can live their unfulfilled dreams in their lives as spirits.

Okri's significant predicaments, as exemplified above, are appropriate to his characters, episodes, and circumstances. The issue raised above proposes that the communal categorize of the novel is in oppression, visited and prohibited by evil men and women and other sundry forces which let loose an assortment of stray vice and evil on the populace. This agrees with what is reachable in our social order today; herein lies the association between art the social order.

Works Cited Primary Source

Okri, Ben. *Songs of Enchantment*. London. Vintage Publishers 1993

Secondary Source

Okara, Gabriel. , *Post Colonial African Writers: A Bio-Bibliographical Critical Sourcebook*. United States of America. Greenwood Press.1998.

How to cite this article?

P.Sankar, "The songs of Sufferings: Position Grand Predicaments Ben Okri in Songs of Enchantment, Infinite Riches, and the Famished Road" Research Journal Of English(RJOE)8(1),PP:49-52,2023, DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.1.52